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**A DISCOURSE ON BELL HOOKS' INTERSECTIONAL APPROACH
TO FEMINISM AND THE INVISIBILITY OF MARGINALIZED
VOICES IN MAINSTREAM FEMINIST MOVEMENTS**

ABSTRACT

This paper examines Bell Hooks' intersectional approach to feminism and its critique of the invisibility of marginalized voices in mainstream feminist movements. Despite feminism's professed goals of equality, its historical focus on the experiences of white, middle-class women has systematically excluded women of colour, working-class women, and other oppressed groups. Hooks' work confronts this exclusion by centring the intersecting oppressions of race, class, and gender, offering a transformative framework for inclusive feminist praxis. The study objectives include analysing Hooks' intersectional critique of mainstream feminism's exclusions, exploring the contributions to feminist theory, pedagogy, and activism, and assessing the enduring relevance of her work in contemporary movements. The paper employs a critical discourse analysis approach, alongside scholarly critiques and case studies of feminist activism. Key findings reveal that intersectionality exposes how single-axis feminism erases Black women's lived experiences, pioneered feminist pedagogy that links education to liberation, and inspired modern movements to adopt inclusive solidarity. The paper concludes that while Hooks' work has reshaped feminism, mainstream movements still struggle to fully integrate marginalized voices, particularly in Global South contexts where colonialism and caste complicate intersectional analysis. Recommendations include centring marginalized narratives in feminist organizing and addressing limitations of materialist and postcolonial perspectives in intersectionality.

Keywords: Bell Hooks, Intersectionality, Feminist Theory, Marginalized Voices, Inclusive Feminism.

INTRODUCTION

Feminist movements have historically been critiqued for centring the experiences of white, middle-class women while marginalizing the voices of women of colour, working-class women, and other oppressed groups. Among the most influential critiques of this exclusionary practice is the work of Bell Hooks (born Gloria Jean Watkins), whose intersectional approach to feminism transformed feminist theory by foregrounding the interconnected oppressions of race, class, and gender. Before the advent of ‘intersectionality,’ Bell Hooks was already emphasizing the interconnected nature of race, class, gender, and other identities in shaping experiences of oppression and privilege. She argues that struggles against sexism must also confront racism, classism, and other forms of discrimination to be effective. Hence, intersectionality recognizes the complex ways various forms of oppression intersect and impact individuals and communities. Emerging in the late 20th century, Hooks challenges mainstream feminism’s narrow focus, arguing that the movement’s failure to address these intersecting systems of power perpetuated inequality and silenced marginalized women (Hooks, 2014; Deckha, 2008).

Bell Hooks (1952–2021) emerged as a transformative figure in feminist theory during the late 20th century, a period marked by the rise of Second Wave feminism in the United States. Hooks’ feminism could be categorized as radical in its goals to transform society fundamentally. Her motives are not just geared towards addressing specific instances of gender inequality but also to challenge and uproot the systemic structures that undermine such inequalities. This includes a critique of patriarchy, capitalism, and other systems of power and domination. Hooks’ feminism is an inclusive movement to end sexist oppression and she asserts that race cannot be separated from gender, history, and class when considering a person. She posits that ‘intersectionality’ refers to intersections of gender, race, class and sexuality to create a ‘white supremacist capitalist patriarchy’ whose ideologies dominate media representation. She contends that black women should develop an ‘oppositional gaze’ that refuses to identify with characters – the ‘gaze’ is political for black Americans, as slaves were punished for looking at their white owners. In her explanation, Hooks gives the rubric that black women are not only underrepresented in film, but that they are not also allowed to ‘look’ either. She explains that looking implores a sense of power that is removed from the black female body, to play the role of object in direct relation to white female existence. While mainstream feminist movements of the 1960s–1980s focused primarily on issues such as reproductive rights, workplace equality, and sexual liberation, Hooks critiqued their failure to address the

intersecting oppressions of race, class, and gender that shaped the lives of Black women and other marginalized groups (Hooks, 2014; Rastogi, 2021).

Her work drew inspiration from Black feminist predecessors like Sojourner Truth, whose 1851 speech “Ain’t I a Woman?” exposed the exclusion of Black women from dominant narratives of womanhood, and later scholars such as Angela Davis and the Combahee River Collective, who articulated the inseparability of racial, economic, and gender justice (Deckha, 2008; Thompson, 2025). Hooks’ seminal text, *Ain’t I a Woman? Black Women and Feminism* (1981) dissects the limitations of Second Wave feminism, arguing that its leadership, predominantly white, middle-class, and college-educated, universalizes their experiences while ignoring the systemic barriers faced by women of colour. She gives hope that feminists around the world can create a mass feminist movement. She criticizes the different phases of American culture and argues that the system is corrupt and that such a system cannot achieve gender equality even if it wants to. She criticizes how the feminist movement at the time defined feminism, stating that it contained a lot of racism and classicism (Hooks, 2014). For instance, the movement’s emphasis on “sisterhood” often obscured racial and class hierarchies, relegating Black women’s struggles against lynching, domestic labour exploitation, and welfare discrimination to the periphery (Al-Hassani, 2022). Hooks contends that this “white feminist” framework not only marginalizes non-white voices but also reinforces the very power structures feminism sought to dismantle (Goodman, 2019).

Though Kimberlé Crenshaw formally coined the term intersectionality in 1989, Hooks’ earlier work laid its theoretical groundwork. She exposes how single-axis analyses of oppression (e.g., gender alone) failed to capture the lived realities of Black women, who faced simultaneous racial and gendered violence (Hooks, 2014; Cseby, 2023). For example, Hooks highlights how Black women’s exclusion from both anti-racist movements (dominated by Black men) and feminist movements (dominated by white women) created a “political blind spot” in advocacy. This critique aligned with what Crenshaw later termed political intersectionality, the phenomenon where marginalized groups fall through the cracks of institutional redress (Deckha, 2008). Hooks’ intersectional lens influences feminist discourses globally. In contexts like India and the UK, her work informs critiques of caste, colonialism, and neoliberal policies that compounded gendered oppression (Rastogi, 2021; Baldwin, 2020). In Nigeria, it informs a critique of traditional patriarchal practices. Today, her ideas remain important in debates about transnational feminism, LGBTQ+ inclusivity, and the

#SayHerName movement, which centres Black women victims of police violence (Biana, 2023; Achiron, 2024). Yet, as this paper explores, mainstream feminism continues to grapple with the visibility of marginalized voices, a testament to the enduring relevance of hooks' critiques.

Furthermore, while intersectionality has become a cornerstone of progressive feminist thought, it has faced significant backlash from conservative scholars and commentators who argue that it fosters division rather than unity. Critics on the right, such as Jordan Peterson and Heather Mac Donald, contend that intersectionality promotes a "hierarchy of victimhood", encouraging identity-based competition rather than collective empowerment (Biana, 2023). Some conservative feminists, like Christina Hoff Sommers, reject intersectionality as overly academic and politically divisive, asserting that it distracts from what they see as feminism's core mission: achieving gender equality in a universalist framework (Baldwin, 2020). These critiques often frame intersectionality as incompatible with liberal individualism, claiming it reduces people to demographic categories rather than recognizing their agency (Cseby, 2023). Even within feminist circles, intersectionality has not been without controversy. Postcolonial feminists argue that Western-centric intersectional frameworks often fail to account for global power imbalances, such as colonialism and imperialism, which shape oppression differently in the Global South (Al-Hassani, 2022). Scholars like Chandra Talpade Mohanty have critiqued intersectionality for sometimes replicating the very exclusions it seeks to address, particularly when applied in contexts where race, class, and gender intersect with neo-colonial economic exploitation (Rastogi, 2021).

Meanwhile, materialist feminists caution that an overemphasis on identity-based analysis can obscure structural economic forces. Theorists such as Nancy Fraser argue that intersectionality, while valuable, risks depoliticizing feminism by shifting focus away from capitalist critique and toward individualized experiences of oppression (Thompson, 2025). These debates highlight tensions within feminist theory about whether intersectionality adequately addresses systemic economic injustice or inadvertently reinforces neoliberal identity politics (Deckha, 2008). However, Bell Hooks anticipated many of these critiques, insisting that intersectionality must remain rooted in activism rather than abstract theory. She argues that a truly liberatory feminism must confront both identity and structural oppression, refusing to separate race, class, and gender from critiques of capitalism and state violence (Hooks, 2014). Her work challenges both conservative dismissals and feminist

oversimplifications by centring praxis, the integration of theory and action, to ensure intersectionality remains a tool for collective liberation rather than academic fragmentation (Nall, 2022).

ROLE OF INTERSECTIONALITY IN FEMINISM

Intersectionality has become a defining framework in contemporary feminist thought, reshaping how scholars and activists understand oppression, privilege, and resistance. It has emerged as both a corrective to mainstream feminism's exclusions and a new paradigm for analysing oppression. While Crenshaw coined the term to describe Black women's legal invisibility in anti-discrimination cases, Hooks' work had already laid the groundwork by demonstrating how feminism's failure to address race and class rendered women of colour structurally invisible (Hooks, 2014; Cseby, 2023). For example, Hooks' critique of Second Wave feminism highlights how white feminists often framed patriarchy as a universal experience, ignoring how Black women faced simultaneous racial and gendered violence; a dynamic later termed "political intersectionality" by Crenshaw (Deckha, 2008). This framework challenged single-axis analyses of oppression, insisting that gender could not be understood in isolation from other identities. Hooks' *Ain't I a Woman?* exemplified this by tracing how Black women's labour, sexuality, and resistance were shaped by slavery, Jim Crow, and capitalism, a legacy that mainstream feminism rarely acknowledged (Hooks, 2014; Thompson, 2025).

Furthermore, intersectionality has transformed feminist activism, inspiring movements like #SayHerName (which centres Black women victims of police violence) and campaigns for trans-inclusive feminism. For instance, the 2017 Women's March faced criticism for initially marginalizing women of colour, prompting organizers to adopt an explicitly intersectional platform, which is a shift reflecting Hooks' insistence on inclusive solidarity (Biana, 2023). However, its adoption has also sparked backlash. Some feminists argue that intersectionality's complexity dilutes activism by prioritizing identity over collective action (Baldwin, 2020). Others, like postcolonial scholars, note its limitations in Global South contexts where imperialism and neoliberalism intersect differently with gender (Al-Hassani, 2022). Even within academia, intersectionality is sometimes reduced to a checklist of identities, betraying its radical roots (Nylander, 2016).

On the other hand, there are debates and evolving challenges. The materialist critique holds that intersectionality's focus on identity can obscure economic structures, urging a return to class analysis (Thompson, 2025). The

conservative co-optation, right-wing movements have weaponized intersectionality as a symbol of "woke excess," despite its origins in Black women's survival strategies (Cseby, 2023). In terms of transnational tensions, while Hooks centred on U.S. Black women, feminists in India and Latin America question whether intersectionality fully captures caste or colonial violence (Rastogi, 2021). In addition, it remains obscure how intersectionality has influenced feminist ideas in Nigeria. Nonetheless, Hooks' work reminds us that intersectionality is not merely theoretical but a call to action. Her feminist pedagogy, for example, applied intersectionality to education, demanding curricula that confront power imbalances (Hooks, 2014; Goodman, 2019). Similarly, her critiques of media representation (e.g., *Black Looks*) showed how intersectionality could dismantle cultural erasure. Its role in feminism is two-fold: to expose the limitations of single-issue movements and to model a feminism that is radically inclusive, one that, as Hooks envisioned, "sees liberation as bound to the liberation of all" (Hooks, 2014; Nall, 2022).

INVISIBILITY OF MARGINALIZED VOICES IN MAINSTREAM FEMINIST MOVEMENTS

Mainstream feminist movements, particularly in the West, have frequently framed gender oppression as a universal experience, disregarding how race, class, and sexuality create vastly different realities for women (Elkholy, 2020; Bhavnani, 2000). The marginalization of voices in mainstream feminist movements manifests in white feminism's dominance, tokenism vs. solidarity, and global feminism & colonial legacies.

The first and second waves of feminism, while ground-breaking in advancing women's rights, were largely shaped by the concerns of white, middle- and upper-class women, often neglecting the intersecting oppressions faced by women of colour, working-class women, and queer women. First-wave feminism (19th–early 20th century) focused on suffrage and legal personhood, but prominent figures like Susan B. Anthony and Elizabeth Cady Stanton often sidelined Black women. For instance, the 1848 Seneca Falls Convention did not include Black women's voices in leadership, and some white suffragists even used racist rhetoric to argue that white women deserved the vote before Black men. Second-wave feminism (1960s–1980s) centred on workplace equality, reproductive rights, and domestic liberation, yet often ignored how Black and Indigenous women had always worked outside the home, not by choice, but due to economic necessity and slavery. While white feminists fought for access to careers, women of colour were already overrepresented in underpaid,

exploitative labour. Feminists like Betty Friedan (1981) spoke of the "problem that has no name," the dissatisfaction of white suburban housewives, but disregarded how Black women, who often worked as domestics in those same households, faced vastly different struggles.

On the other hand, tokenism vs. solidarity shows the illusion of inclusion (Omotoso & Olaronke, 2024). As mainstream feminism has become more racially diverse in rhetoric, women of colour are often included as symbolic gestures rather than as equal contributors shaping feminist theory and activism. Feminist organizations and media may feature a few women of colour in leadership or panels to appear inclusive, but their perspectives are rarely centred in policy-making or movement priorities. Women of colour are expected to speak for entire communities, often without institutional support (Hocart, 1931). For example, Black feminists like Angela Davis or Kimberlé Crenshaw are frequently cited in discussions on race and gender, but their critiques of capitalism and state violence are rarely integrated into the mainstream feminist agenda. Mainstream feminism sometimes adopts the language of intersectionality without addressing material inequalities. True solidarity would require redistributing power, amplifying marginalized feminists not as tokens, but as leaders, redefining feminist goals.

Furthermore, global feminism and colonial legacies reveal Western feminism's imperial blind spots (Musingafi & Musingafi, 2014; Elkholy, 2020; Bhavnani, 2000). Western feminist movements have often universalized their struggles, assuming that the liberation of white women in Europe and North America represents progress for all women. This ignores how colonialism, imperialism, and neoliberal capitalism shape gender oppression in the Global South. Some Western feminists frame women in the Global South as passive victims needing rescue (e.g., campaigns focusing solely on banning the hijab without considering Muslim women's own feminist movements). While Western feminists fight for equal pay, multinational corporations exploit women in sweatshops in Bangladesh, Honduras, or Cambodia, where labour rights are minimal, and unions are suppressed. Mainstream feminism rarely connects these struggles. Global feminist initiatives led by Western NGOs often impose top-down solutions, side-lining grassroots movements led by local women.

NEXUS OF BELL HOOKS' INTERSECTIONALITY AND MARGINALIZED VOICES IN MAINSTREAM FEMINIST MOVEMENTS

Hooks revolutionized feminist theory by centering the intersections of race, class, and gender, challenging the movement's historical exclusion of Black women and other marginalized groups. Her work not only redefines feminist scholarship but also bridges the gap between academia and grassroots activism, insisting that theory must inform tangible liberation. This section explores Hooks' key contributions, from her foundational critiques of white feminism to her development of feminist pedagogy and her enduring influence on contemporary social justice movements.

Pioneering Intersectional Feminism: Long before Kimberlé Crenshaw coined the term intersectionality, Hooks exposes how mainstream feminism universalized the struggles of white, middle-class women while ignoring the compounded oppressions faced by Black women. In *Ain't I a Woman?* and *Black Women and Feminism* (1981), she traced the historical devaluation of Black womanhood from slavery's exploitation of Black women's labour to the racist-sexist stereotypes that persisted in the 20th century (Hooks, 2014). By highlighting how systems of racism, sexism, and capitalism are intertwined, Hooks dismantled the myth of a monolithic "female experience" and laid the groundwork for intersectional analysis (Deckha, 2008; Thompson, 2025). According to her, feminism is not simply a struggle to end male chauvinism; it is a commitment to eradicating the ideology of domination that permeates Western culture (Hooks, 1984).

Critique of White Feminism and Call for Inclusivity: Hooks' sharpest critiques targeted Second Wave feminism's exclusionary practices, which framed gender oppression in isolation from race and class. She argues that figures like Betty Friedan, while advocating for white women's liberation, ignored how Black women had always worked outside the home, often in exploitative roles (Hooks, 2014; Al-Hassani, 2022). This critique reveals a blind spot in feminist activism: the conflation of women's issues with white women's issues. Her solution was a radically inclusive feminism that centred marginalized voices (e.g., poor women, women of colour), rejected elitist academic jargon, made theory accessible, and embraced men as allies in dismantling patriarchy (Hooks, 2014; Goodman, 2019).

Feminist Pedagogy: Education as Liberation: Hooks extended her intersectional framework to education, advocating for engaged pedagogy, which

is a teaching practice that connects learning to real-world struggles. In *Teaching to Transgress* (1994), she argues that classrooms must be sites of critical consciousness, where students and teachers collaboratively confront systems of power (Nylander, 2016). For example, her impact on curriculum reform pushes for syllabi that include Black feminist thought and critique Eurocentric narratives, on classroom dynamics rejected hierarchical teacher-student relationships, emphasizing mutual respect and dialogue, and on praxis over theory insisted education should inspire activism, not passive consumption of ideas (Hooks, 2014; Biana, 2023).

Cultural Criticism: Media and Representation: Hooks' analyses of pop culture (e.g., *Black Looks: Race and Representation*, 1992) exposes how media perpetuated racist and sexist tropes. She dissects films, music, and advertising to show how Black women were either invisible or reduced to stereotypes (e.g., the "Jezebel" or "Mammy" archetypes). Her work remains foundational in critical race and gender studies.

Legacy and Contemporary Relevance: Hooks' ideas continue to shape movements like #MeToo, reproductive justice activism, and LGBTQ+ advocacy, all of which now prioritize intersectionality. However, her work also faces critiques. For example, Postcolonial Feminists argue that her U.S.-centric lens overlooks global imperialism (Rastogi, 2021). Materialist Critics claim her focus on identity sometimes obscures economic structures (Thompson, 2025). Yet, Hooks' insistence on love as a political force—articulated in *All About Love* (2000)—remains a touchstone for activists seeking to build inclusive, compassionate movements (Nall, 2022).

Table 1: Bell Hooks' Contribution to Feminism

Contribution	Impact
Intersectional Critique	Exposed white feminism's exclusions paved the way for Crenshaw's work.
Accessible Theory	Wrote in clear prose to democratize feminist knowledge.
Feminist Pedagogy	Transformed education into a tool for liberation.
Cultural Analysis	Revealed how the media reinforces racial-sexual oppression.
Love as Praxis	Framed love as essential to justice work.

IMPACT OF HOOKS' INTERSECTIONAL APPROACH ON THE INVISIBILITY OF MARGINALIZED VOICES IN MAINSTREAM FEMINIST MOVEMENTS

Bell Hooks' contributions to feminist theory have had a profound and lasting impact on both academic discourse and grassroots activism. Her emphasis on the interplay of personal sensibilities and criticality reshaped the landscape of feminist politics, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of gender issues that incorporates emotional and intellectual investments in knowledge production. By advocating for self-reflexivity in gender activism, Hooks has encouraged activists to engage critically with their own experiences and the institutional frameworks that shape them, thus fostering a transformative dialectic between lived experiences and academic theories.

Significance in Feminist Movements: Hooks' work has been instrumental in shaping a generation of feminists who continue to navigate the complexities of gender, race, and class in their activism. Her accessible writing style, which is rooted in real-life implications and emotional resonance, has made feminist theory more approachable to a broader audience (Deckha, 2008). As a result, Hooks' ideas have transcended the academic realm, becoming a part of everyday discussions about equality and justice, thus contributing to the ongoing evolution of feminist movements.

Intersectionality and Inclusivity: A core aspect of Hooks' legacy is her insistence on addressing the intersections of race, gender, and class. By highlighting the importance of understanding how these categories overlap, Hooks challenges mainstream feminist narratives that often exclude the experiences of women of colour and those from marginalized backgrounds (Deckha, 2008). Her work laid the groundwork for the development of intersectionality as a critical framework in feminist studies, enabling a richer analysis of the varied experiences of oppression that women face (Deckha, 2008). This intersectional approach has opened pathways for more inclusive feminist discourses that seek to amplify marginalized voices, ensuring that their perspectives are no longer rendered invisible.

Challenges and Critiques: Despite her significant contributions, Hooks' theories have faced scrutiny in recent debates surrounding race and gender within feminism. Critics have examined her frameworks from postcolonial and transnational perspectives, questioning the applicability of her ideas in addressing contemporary racial and gendered issues. However, such critiques also highlight the relevance of Hooks' work in ongoing discussions about

inclusivity and the evolution of feminist thought. In this context, Hooks remains a pivotal figure whose ideas continue to resonate in current feminist movements and scholarship.

Continuing Influence: The influence of Hooks' work can be seen in various feminist discourses today, particularly as new generations of activists grapple with the complexities of identity politics and social justice. Her call for critical consciousness and emotional awareness in activism resonates strongly in today's digital landscape, where young activists often engage in social media to challenge injustices (Nylander, 2016). By encouraging individuals to confront their internalized beliefs and engage in meaningful self-reflection, Hooks has left a legacy that emphasizes personal responsibility as a foundation for collective action.

CONCLUSION

Bell Hooks' intersectional approach to feminism fundamentally reshapes feminist discourse by exposing how mainstream movements historically marginalized women of colour, working-class women, and other oppressed groups, demonstrating that systems of race, class, and gender oppression are inextricably linked. Despite Hooks' profound contributions, this paper has revealed that mainstream feminism continues to grapple with inclusivity. Hooks' legacy endures as a call to action. Her vision of feminism, rooted in love, critical consciousness, and collective liberation, remains essential for building movements that truly center the most marginalized. Therefore, feminists must commit to amplifying underrepresented voices, integrating intersectional pedagogy into education, and confronting the economic and structural dimensions of oppression. Only then can feminism fulfil its promise of justice for all women. Finally, Hooks' work reminds us that feminism is not merely an intellectual exercise but a lifelong practice of resistance and solidarity. As contemporary activists navigate evolving challenges from digital advocacy to transnational organizing, the intersectionality framework offers both a compass and a challenge to create a feminism that is as inclusive in practice as it is in principle.

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